

Synthesis of New Mero- and Asymmetrical Pyrazolo-Monomethine Cyanine Dyes.

ZARIF H. KHALIL and ABDU E. ABDEL-RAHMAN

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt, A.R.E.

Manuscript received 29 November 1976, accepted 17 May 1977

New isatylidene mero cyanine dyes (II) were prepared through the reaction of isatin (I) with 2-methyl quaternary salts in presence of a basic catalyst. Interaction of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone derivatives (III) with α -picoline- and quinaldine-ethiodides in presence of triethylamine afforded the asymmetrical pyrazolo-2'-monomethine cyanines (V). Meanwhile, the use of piperidine gave the aldol intermediate (IV), which dehydrated to the corresponding cyanine dye (V). Structural configurations were identified by i.r. and v.s. spectral determination.

MERO cyanine dyes containing cyclic keto group which are listed in the literature are beyond estimation, and they are used as photosensitisers¹⁻⁶, electron acceptors⁴, electrophotography⁷ and filter dyes^{4,8}; but, those containing isatylidene residue was not mentioned before. Recently, it was stated by B. Lal, *et al*⁹, that the condensation reaction of pyridine-2,3- and 4-carboxaldehyde with substituted 2-oxindole gave the corresponding 3-isatylidene derivatives, and the 2-pyridyl isomer possesses high diuretic activity. Within these respects, 3-isatylidene-2-(pyridino-, quinolino- and benzoxazolo-ethiodides)-mero cyanine dyes(II) were prepared.

Also, asymmetrical pyrazolo-2'-monomethine cyanine dyes(V) were obtained through the reaction of 5-pyrazolone derivatives with 2-methyl quaternary salts in

presence of triethylamine. On the other hand, the use of piperidine, gave the aldol intermediate (IV), which dehydrated to the corresponding cyanine dye (V)¹⁰. It is of interest to mention that, the asymmetrical-2'-monomethine cyanine dyes are widely used as photosensitisers in the blue-green light¹¹⁻¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

The condensation reaction between 2-methyl quaternary salts and isatin (I) takes place at the more active 3-carbonyl group (within isatin nucleus) in presence of a basic catalyst, giving 3-isatylidene-2'-(pyridino-, quinolino-, and benzoxazolo-ethiodides) mero cyanine dyes(II). The reaction is represented as follows :

IIa ; A = pyridine
b ; A = quinoline
c ; A = benzoxazole

The mero cyanine dyes (IIa-c) are readily soluble in polar organic solvents with an orange to violet colour and their ethanolic solutions gave a yellow colour in acidic medium turned violet on basification with alkali hydroxide. The reversible change in colour gives an indication to their use as acid-base indicator in protometric titrations. IR spectra of (IIa-c) showed a well defined absorption band at $\sim 1725 - 1703 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to α - β unsaturated ketone in a 5-membered ring.

The v.s. absorption spectra of (IIa, A=pyridine) in ethanol showed a strong absorption band located at λ_{max} 405 nm, ϵ_{max} 14,000 with a shoulder at λ_{max} 385 nm, ϵ_{max} 13,690 and another band at a longer wavelength attributed to intramolecular charge transfer (C.T.) located at λ_{max} 550 nm, ϵ_{max} 4,950. Substituting of the quaternary heterocyclic moiety, pyridyl-by quinolyl- (IIb, A=quinoline) causes a strong red shift in the longer wave length (C.T.) by 120 nm, with the

TABLE 1—3-ISATYLIDINE-2'-[PYRIDINO-, QUINOLINO-BENZOXAZOLO-ETHIOLIDES]-MERO-CYANINE DYES (IIA-C)

Compound No.	m. p. °C	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield % theory	Formula	Analysis %		Absorption spectra	
					Calcd N	Found N	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}
IIa	300	Ethanol	45	$C_{16}H_{15}N_2OI$	7.40	7.28	385 (sh), 405, 550	13,690 ; 14,000, 4,950
IIb	247	Methanol	58	$C_{20}H_{17}N_2OI$	6.54	6.48	430, 525 (sh), 565, 610 (sh), 670	600, 630, 770, 420, 118
IIc	300	n-Butanol	37	$C_{19}H_{15}N_2O_2I$	6.69	6.73	256, 374, 412 (sh), 546	20,400 ; 23,000, 20,150 ; 16,600

The analysis for carbon and hydrogen are satisfactory, (sh)=shoulder.

III, X = H, n-Bu-, sec. Bu- and benzyl-

IV, X = sec. Bu, A = C_6H_5 .

V, A = H, a ; X = H

b ; X = n-Bu-

c ; X = sec. Bu

d ; X = benzyl-

V, A = C_6H_5 , e ; X = H

f ; X = n-Bu

g ; X = sec. Bu

h ; X = benzyl

decrease in its molar extension coefficient, λ_{max} 670 nm, ϵ_{max} 118. While substituting by benzoxyazoyl-, causes a slight blue shift by 4 nm with strong intensification of the absorption band, (IIc, A=benzoxazole) λ_{max} 546 nm, ϵ_{max} 16,600 (c.f Table 1).

The reaction of 5-pyrazolone and its 4-alkyl derivatives (III) with α -picoline- and quinaldine-ethiodides was found to be greatly affected by the reaction conditions and the type of basic catalyst used. Thus, the use of triethylamine, the condensation reaction proceeded to give directly the expected asymmetrical 5-[3-methyl-1-phenyl-(4-alkyl substituted) pyrazolo]-2'-[pyridinium (quinolinium) 1-ethiodide] monomethine cyanines (V); while, using piperidine, the aldol intermediate (IV) was isolated here thermally dehydrated to the corresponding cyanine dye (V). The reaction is shown :

The aldol intermediate is colourless needles, readily soluble in alcohols and its i.r. spectra showed a well defined absorption band at ~ 3520 cm^{-1} attributed to OH group,

The asymmetrical pyrazolo-2'-monomethine cyanines (V) possess different colours ranged from orange to deep violet, easily soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid from which iodine was liberated on heating. Cyanine dyes containing quaternary quinoline residue (Ve-h; A=C₈H₄) exhibit a strong green fluorescence in solutions, which was not observed in those containing quaternary pyridine residue (Va-d, A=H).

The v.s. absorption spectra of (V, A=C₈H₄) in ethanol consist of different bands, their position and molar extinction coefficient are influenced by the type of 4-substituent (X) in the pyrazolo nucleus. The absorption spectra of (Ve, X=H) shows an absorption band at λ_{max} 375 nm, ϵ_{max} 1,100 and another band at a longer wave-length attributed to intramolecular charge transfer (C.T.) located at λ_{max} 478 nm, ϵ_{max} 1,800. Substituting 4-hydrogen by n-butyl (Vf, X=n-Bu) causes a strong red shift in C.T. band by 90 nm; λ_{max}

568, ϵ_{max} 5,500. This red shift is attributed to the increase in both mass molecule and its coplanarity. On the other hand, substituting by sec-butyl (Vg, X=sec. Bu) having the same mass molecule, causes a slight blue shift relative to (Ve, X=H) by 3 nm; λ_{max} 475 nm, ϵ_{max} 17,490. This blue shift may be due to the bulky effect of the branched alkyl side chain (i.e. due to the α -substituted methyl group) which affect the coplanarity of the molecule leading to the increase in the excitation energy, absorbing at a shorter wave-length (cf. Table 3).

Experimental

The i.r. spectra were determined with a Perkin-Elmer Infrared 137 B. Spectrophotometer, v.s. spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP 8000 ultraviolet recording spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells. Melting points are not corrected.

Synthesis of 3-isatylidene-2'-[pyridino-, quinolino- and benzoxazolo-ethiodides]-mero cyanines (II) : A mixture of 2-methyl quaternary salt (α -picoline-, quinaldine- and 2-methyl benzoxazole-ethiodides) (0.006 mol), isatin (I) (0.005 mol), ethanol (50 ml) and piperidine ($\sim$ one ml) was heated for 90 minutes at 70°. The reaction mixture was concentrated to $\sim$ 30 ml at reduced pressure where the mero cyanine dyes (II) were separated, they were collected, washed with few ml. methanol, then with ether and crystallised from the proper solvent. The results are given in Table 1.

Synthesis of asymmetrical 5-[3-methyl-1-phenyl-(4-alkyl substituted) pyrazolo]-2'-[pyridinium (quinolinium)-1-ethiodide]-monomethine cyanine dyes (V) : A mixture of α -picoline-(quinaldine) ethiodides (0.006 mol), 3-methyl-1-phenyl-(4-substituted alkyl)-5-pyrazolone (0.005 mol), triethylamine (1.5 ml) and ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 hours on a water bath. The reaction mixture was concentrated to $\sim$ 20 ml. and poured onto a stirred ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid. The separated cyanine dyes (V) were collected, washed with water, then with ether and crystallised from the proper solvents. The results are given in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 2—ASYMMETRICAL 5-[3-METHYL-1-PHENYL-(4-ALKYL)-PYRAZOLO]-2'-[PYRIDINIUM-1-ETHIODIDE]-MONOMETHINE CYANINE DYES (Va-d) (A=H).

Compound No.	m. p. °C	Solvent of crystal	Yield % theory	Formula	Analysis %		Absorption spectra	
					Calcd.	Found	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .
					N	N		
Va	156	Methanol	42	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₈ I	10.87	10.18	394	4,500
Vb	159	Ethanol	51	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₈ I	9.11	8.97	345, 500 (sh)	5,400; 4,400
Vc	130	Ethanol/water	38	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₈ I	9.11	9.23	390	5,100
Vd	90	„ „	40	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₈ I	9.48	9.35	496 (sh)	11,700

The analyses for carbon and hydrogen are satisfactory.

TABLE 3—ASYMMETRICAL 5-[3-METHYL-1-PHENYL-(4-ALKYL)-PYRAZOLO]-2'-QUINOLINIUM-1-ETHIODE] (Ve-h, A=C₆H₄).

Compound No.	m.p. °C	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield % Theory	Formula	Analysis %		Colour of ethanolic solution		Absorption spectra	
					Calcd N	Found N	H ₂ SO ₄ (0.1 N)	NaOH (0.1 N)	λ _{max}	ε _{max}
Ve	199	Ethanol	67	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₃ I	9.23	9.32	Yellow	Orange red	375, 478	1,100; 1,800
Vf	108	Methanol	72	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ I	8.22	8.14	Yellow	Violet	428 (sh), 506 568	3,225; 4,540 5,500
Vg	140	Ethanol/ ether	55	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ I	8.22	8.00	Yellow	Orange	378, 475	9,900; 17,490
Vh	110	Ethanol/ ether	65	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ N ₃ I	7.70	7.64	Yellow	Violet	325, 480 (sh), 518, 560	4,175; 2,630 4,300; 5,980

The analyses for carbon and hydrogen are satisfactory.

Synthesis of the aldol intermediate (IV): A mixture of quinaldine ethiodide (0.006 mol), 3 methyl-1-phenyl-4-sec. butyl-5-pyrazolone (III), ethanol (50 ml) and piperidine (1.5 ml) was refluxed for 3 hours on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was concentrated and cooled, where colourless needles were separated after 3 days at room temperature. The product was collected, washed with alcohol, then with ether and crystallised from ethanol-water mixture (1:1) into colourless needles, m.p. 108°, yield 42%. Analysis calculated for C₂₄H₂₂N₃OI: N, 7.93. Found: 7.87%.

Dehydration of (IV) was carried out by heating the solid material at 123–5° for 15 minutes. The cyanine dyes (V) has a m.p. and mixed m.p. 140°.

References

- 1a. J. ERNST POPPE, Ger (East) 71, 445, (Cl. G. 03c), 20 Feb. 1970, Appl. 18 Jul. 1968.
- 1b. OSKAV RIESTER, HANS OEHLISCHLAGER and HEINRICH ODENWAELDER (Agfa-Gevaert A.—G.) Ger. Offen. 2, 142, 967, 08 Mar. 1973.
2. FRANK G. WEBSTER and G. S. LESLIE BROOKER, (Eastman Kodak Co.) U.S. 3, 743, 638, 03 Jul. 1973; Appl. 21, 210, 19 Mar. 1970.
3. HENRI DEPOORTE and H. THEOFIEL GHYS (Agfa-Gevaert A.—G.) Ger. Offen. 2, 102, 176(Cl. C09 b), 29 Jul. 1971; Brit. Appl. 20 Jan. 1970.
4. EARL J. VAN LARE, (Eastman Kodak Co.) U.S. 3, 615, 608 (Cl. 96/101; G03c, C09b), 26 Oct. 1971; Appl. 23 Dec. 1966, 24, Apr. 1970.
5. SALVATORE EMMI, (GAF Corp.) U.S. 3, 563, 735, (Cl. 96-1-7, G03g), 16 Feb. 1971, Appl. 15 Jul. 1968.
6. GEOFFREY E. FICKEN, (Ilford Ltd.) Brit. 1, 253, 468 (Cl. C09b, G03c), 17 Nov. 1971, Appl. 03 Jul. 1969.
7. HONRI DEPOORTER and JOZEF R. SCHELLEKENS, (Agfa-Gevaert N. V.) Belg. 768, 214, 08 Dec. 1971; Brit. Appl. 28, 144/70, 10 Jun. 1970.
8. FREDERICK J. SAUTER (Eastman Kodak Co.), Fr. Demande 2, 198, 881, (Cl. C09b, G03c) 08 Mar. 1974; U.S. Appl. 266. 028, 26 June 1972.
9. B. LAL, PRATAP SINGH, A. P. BHADURI and K. KAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13(9), 898-903.
10. SHERRILL A. PUCKETT, IAIN C. PAUL and DAVID Y. CURTIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98(3), 787-92.
11. A. I. TOLMACHEV and E. F. KAROBAN, *Ukr. Khim. Zh.*, 1970, 36(5), 478-83.
12. N. S. KOZLOV, O. D. ZHIKHAREVA and S. A. BATISHCHE, *Khim. Geterotski. Soedin.*, 1972, 12, 1619-21.
13. F. M. HAMER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 206.
14. L. G. S. BROOKER and G. H. KEYES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2488; L. G. S. BROOKER, G. H. KEYES and F. L. WHITE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2492; L. G. S. BROOKER and Eastman Kodak Co., U.S. 1, 969, 446, (7 Aug. 1934); U.S. 2, 143, 839, (17 Jan. 1939).
15. W. J. HICKINBOTTOM, Reaction of organic compounds; Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., Third Edition, 1957, 553.